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Research Article

**INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN
EMPLOYEES' SPIRITUAL LEADERSHIP, ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST
AND JOB INVOLVEMENT AT AHVAZ JUNDISHAPUR UNIVERSITY OF
MEDICAL SCIENCES, IN SOUTHWEST OF IRAN****Gholamhossein Barekat¹ and Nastaran Sabbaghi^{*2}**¹ Associate Professor, Department of Educational Administration, Ahvaz Branch, Islamic Azad University, Ahvaz, Iran² PhD Student, Department of Educational Administration, Ahvaz Branch, Islamic Azad University, Ahvaz, Iran**Abstract:**

Introduction: This study is carried out to investigate the simple and multiple relationships between spiritual leadership and organizational trust with job involvement among staff members of Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences, in Southwest of Iran.

Materials and Methods: The subjects of this study were 384 non-faculty members of the university who were selected randomly from the community of about 7739 by using the Cochran formula. The subjects responded to the Spiritual Leadership Questionnaire of Fry et al. (2005), Edward Zukil Patrick job involvement questionnaire (1984), and Morgan's et al. (1998) Organizational trust scale. In order to analyze the data, in addition to descriptive methods (frequency, frequency percentage, ...), for analyzing the research hypotheses, inferential statistics including Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple regression were used by the means of SPSS-16 software.

Results: The results showed that separately there is a positive and significant relationship between spiritual leadership, organizational trust, and job involvement. There is also a multivariate relationship between these variables so that the results of regression analysis showed that one could predict the job involvement from spiritual leadership and organizational trust, while the share of spiritual leadership was higher so that 64% of job involvement variance is explained by spiritual leadership. The significance level in this study was $\alpha = 0.000$.

Discussion and Conclusion: By training the right leadership methods and raising the level of organizational trust in the staff, it is possible to improve their relationships with each other as well as to create an attachment to the job to improve their efficiency in the organization.

Key Words: Spiritual Leadership, Organizational Trust, Job involvement, Employees, Ahvaz, Iran.

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INTRODUCTION:

Skilled, educated and empowered manpower is considered as the most important factor in the development of societies and organizations (1-2). Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences is one of the most popular universities in ministry of health and medical education with over 1700 years of age (4-3). Every year, many elites in order to continue studying (7-6-5) as well as to recruit as faculty members enter the universities of medical sciences in Iran (10-9-8). The universities of medical sciences are training the specialized and committed forces of the community in the field of health care (11-13-12). Spiritual leadership is one of the approaches that have been seriously raised in the theoretical foundations of leadership and management in the last decades of the 20th century. The Spiritual Leadership movement includes leadership serving models, employee participation and empowering them based on the philosophy of servant leadership (14). The spiritual leader is one who, in dealing with organizational situations, instead of interfering in affairs, shows inspiration; instead of controlling, trust, instead of imposing restrictions, independence, rather than acting, imaging, and modesty rather than showing off (15). Spiritual Leadership can be seen as a phenomenon when one can see that a person in a leadership position is a manifestation of spiritual values such as honesty, truth, and humility, and shows himself as an example of a person who can be trusted. (16). Therefore, spiritual leadership is related to learning and development, and it is necessary for organizations that are inclined to succeed and progress. The organization's spiritual leadership through growth and learning ultimately leads the organization to continuous improvement in operations as well as higher-quality products and services, and ultimately leads to a higher level of customer satisfaction, and then better financial performance (17). Korthuis-Smith's concluded that participatory leadership, people's decisions, organizational support, performance feedback, and improvement of situations are completely related to trust (18). In addition, staff positive assessments of supervisors' performance will lead to higher levels of organizational trust (19). Therefore, trust in manager plays a key role in achieving leadership goals. Greenleaf believes that trust is a turning point for organization leadership since legitimacy of leadership begins with trust. Trust and respect will increase in circumstances that in society, the responsibility of each person towards each other and the responsibility of everyone towards a person must be unlimited. Greenleaf showed that organizational trust was created when the authorities (leaders) were accepted as officials because they

understood the organization and think about all the people of the organization. He noted that leaders are responsible for the levels and types of organizational performance that they deserve to be trusted (20). So, according to Greenleaf, leadership is the result and introduction to trust in leadership and organizational trust. This may be due to the fact that trusted leadership increases the understanding of leadership (21). On the other hand, most of the recent studies in the field of behavior are about the attitudes of individuals in their own work organizations. Among these attitudes, the term occupational or job attachment is a new concept in line with organizational behavior. Job involvement (consider the job as a factor that introduces you) refers to the degree to which a person identifies his or her job as a factor for introducing him or her and consider his or her work or function as a pride and prestige and does his or her job in terms of components such as affiliation, consistency, loyalty, acceptance of goals and the desire to apply endeavor to realize them. Or, in other words, how much the person is doing and actually spending time with his job (22). Job involvement is an interesting and growing research topic. It is defined as a brief belief of the current occupation that leads to action and can meet the needs of the individual (Manther, 2005). Therefore, involvement level is of interest to managers and policy makers because job involvement is effective in organizational performance and effectiveness (24). Zolansky et al. (2004) in their research found that the value of perceived trust in the source would be effective in transferring knowledge within the organization. Mooradian, Renzl, and Matzler (2005) also found that trust has a positive and significant relationship with the sharing of knowledge within and between groups. Yusof and Tahir (2011) presented a framework for investigating the relationship between spiritual leadership theory and job satisfaction in a multidimensional approach. The dimensions of spiritual leadership in their models were prospect, love for altruism, hope or faith, membership, and meaningfulness and indicators of job satisfaction, work, payment, promotion, supervision, and colleagues. Frye and Sloukam (2008) in their study showed that spiritual leadership, by drawing faith as a vision and a culture of excellence, positively and significantly affects spiritual well-being and organizational-personnel performance variables, which ultimately increase the level of welfare, health, and well-being of the staff. Cohen and Veled-Hecht (2008) in a study between nurses working in a hospital concluded that there was a positive and significant relationship between social organization, distributive justice, procedural justice, emotional commitment, professional commitment,

occupational attachment. Findings of the research by Gaultz (2001), Bamberand Sharp (2003), Pal (2004), Carlos (2005), Adalat Khan (2007) showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational trust and organizational excellence.

- ✓ Therefore, according to what was said, the main purpose of the present research is to investigate the effect of spiritual leadership on organizational trust and the prediction of employees' job involvement on spiritual leadership and organizational trust. The present study also seeks to examine the following hypotheses:
 - There is a relationship between spiritual leadership and organizational trust.
 - There is a relationship between spiritual leadership and job involvement.
 - There is a relationship between organizational trust and job involvement.
 - Job involvement, spiritual leadership, and organizational trust have common share.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Since this research attempts to investigate the relationships between the variables studied (spiritual leadership, organizational trust, and job involvement), the present study is a correlational study and considering that the necessary data for analyzing relationships has been obtained through the views and ideas of individuals (by using a questionnaire) this correlation is a survey. The statistical population of this research was all non-faculty members of Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences and this number was 7739 (including employee and manager) at the time of the research. The sample size is estimated at 384 people using the Cochran formula. In this research, random sampling method was used to select the sample. Data collection was done by three questionnaires of Spiritual Leadership Frye et al. (2005), Edward Zukil Patrick's job involvement questionnaire (1984) and Morgan's et al. (1998) Organizational trust scale. The Fry's et al. Spiritual Leadership questionnaire was designed in 2005 in the form of a five-point Likert spectrum (Fry, Vitucci, and Cedillo, 2012). The Spiritual Leadership Questionnaire included two sections of general questions and specialized questions. General questions, including five items of age, sex, service record and marital status, and the job group and specialized questions were also based on the purpose of the research, including the questions related to the variables under study. The number of

specialized questions in the questionnaire was 25 and it was designed in the five-point Likert scale; from 1 (very disagree) to 5, (totally agree). In the mentioned questionnaire a total of 31 questions for 7 dimensions of spiritual leadership were designed, so that each dimension had several questions. These questions assess 7 dimensions of perspective (questions 1-3), love for altruism (questions 4 to 9), faith (questions 10 to 12), meaningfulness (questions 13-15), membership (questions 16-18), organizational commitment (questions 19 to 22) and performance feedback (questions 23 to 25). In the studies of Rastgar, Jangholi, Heidari and Heidari (2012), questionnaire Cronbach's alpha obtained as 0.95. The Cronbach's alpha of Spiritual Leadership Questionnaire has been determined to be 0.88 in Ziaei et al research. Also, in Abbaspour, Rahimian and Araee (2014), the Cronbach's alpha of this scale was 0.92. In this study, Cronbach's alpha was 0.93. The Job Involvement Questionnaire was developed by Edward Zukil Patrick in 1984 and includes 20 items. The scoring method is based on a 4-point scale, so that in positive items 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,12,15,20 the choices I totally disagree with the options, I disagree, agree and totally agree, scores of 3,2,1,0 are assigned and in the negative items (10,11,13,14,16,17,18,19), the reverse -coding method is evident, that is, I completely disagree with the options, I disagree, agree, I totally agree, have the scores 0,1,2,3. A maximum score of 60 indicates a very high attachment and a minimum score of 0 indicates a very low attachment. In this study, Cronbach's alpha was 0.88. The Moorman, Blakely and Niehoff 8-item organizational trust questionnaire has also been used to assess the organizational trust, which has been verified by Gholparvar and Arizi (2006) in Iran. The responding scale of this questionnaire was on a 5-point Likert scale (I totally disagree = 1 to fully agree = 5), and the reliability and re-test coefficients were 0.79 and 0.84, respectively. Predictive criterion validity of organizational trust scale in Golparvar and Arizi (2006) research was verified and confirmed in a set of 319 people. In this study, Cronbach's alpha was 0.81.

RESULTS:

As seen in Table 1, the average and standard deviation of subjects in the spiritual leadership variable are 79.30 and 324.55, respectively. The mean and standard deviation of the subjects in the organizational trust variable are respectively: 26.71 and 12.69 respectively. The mean and standard deviation of the subjects in the job involvement variables were 53.77 and 72.28, respectively.

Table 1: Average, standard deviation, minimum and maximum variables of research

Variables	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.
Spiritual Leadership	79/30	324.55	39	125
Organizational Trust	26/71	12.59	16	40
Job Involvement	53/77	72.28	36	94

As shown in Table 2, the correlation coefficient between spiritual leadership and organizational trust in the subjects by using Pearson correlation is $r = 0.51$. Since this correlation coefficient is significant at $P < 0.001$.

Table 2: Simple correlation coefficients between spiritual leadership and organizational trust in subjects

Criterion variable	Indicators Predictor variable	Count	Correlation Coefficient (R)	Sig.
Organizational Trust	Spiritual Leadership	384	0.51	0.000

As shown in Table 3, the correlation coefficient between spiritual leadership and job involvement in the subjects by using Pearson correlation is $r = 0.49$. Since this correlation coefficient is significant at $P < 0.001$.

Table 3: Simple correlation coefficients between spiritual leadership and job involvement in subjects

Criterion variable	Indicators Predictor variable	Count	Correlation Coefficient (R)	Sig.
Job Involvement	Spiritual Leadership	384	0.49	0.000

As shown in Table 4, the correlation coefficient between organizational trust and job involvement in the subjects by using Pearson correlation is $r = 0.54$. Since this correlation coefficient is significant at $P < 0.29$ level.

Table 4: Simple correlation coefficients between organizational trust and job involvement in subjects

Criterion variable	Indicators Predictor variable	Count	Correlation Coefficient (R)	Sig.
Job Involvement	Organizational Trust	384	0.54	0.291

Table 5: The results of regression analysis of predictive variables with job involvement by simultaneous method for subjects

Criterion variable	Indicators Predictive Variable	MR	RS	FP	Regression coefficients	
					1	2
Job involvement	Spiritual Leadership	0.50	0.25	63.64 $P < 0.000$	$\beta = 0.51$ $t = 11.21$ $P < 0.000$	
	Organizational Trust	-	-	-	$\beta = 0.51$ $t = 11.21$ $P < 0.000$	$\beta = 0.51$ $t = 11.21$ $P < 0.000$

As seen in Table 5, regression results are confirmed concurrently and the spiritual leadership and organizational trust variables are predictive of job involvement and these variables have multiple relationships with job involvement. In the meantime, the share of spiritual leadership is greater, and spiritual leadership is more effective in predicting job involvement. R and R^2 are respectively 0.50 and 0.25, and it can be said that 63.64 of the variance of job involvement of personnel employed in Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences is explained by the variable of spiritual leadership.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between spiritual leadership and organizational trust with job involvement. In the present study, according to the results of research hypotheses and previous researches, the findings indicate that there is a positive and significant relationship between the variables of spiritual

leadership, organizational trust, and job involvement. Also, the results of regression analysis indicate that that one can predict the job involvement from spiritual leadership and organizational trust. This suggests that the results of this research are in line with past research of researchers such as Lambert, Hogan, and Griffin, (2009), Zafarizadeh, (2003); Laschinger et al., (2006); job involvement, (2011); Fry and Slocum, (2005); Zafarizadeh, (2003) and Chaudhary, (2005).

Manpower of each organization is the expensive source of the organization that can help it to achieve its goals. (26,27,28) By affirming the existence of a relationship between job involvement and the motivation for advancement, the level of involvement is of interest to managers and policy makers because job involvement is effective in organizational performance and effectiveness. On the other hand, the goal of spiritual leadership is to pay attention to the basic needs of followers in order to

provide their spiritual survival. This spiritual leadership will make employees understand the true meaning of their jobs and pay attention to their jobs. Unfortunately, evidence suggests that the performance and commitment of the workforce and work organization in Iran's state organizations are low, employees do not perform their assigned duties well, they have low motivation and working relationships, have little job satisfaction, and always want to leave the organization and change their job. These evidences indicate a low commitment to work and organization, which seems to be due to their low level of trust in the organization. Therefore, in this context, university officials and those who work with staff and personnel working in organizational units are recommended to consider these three variables more than ever and these three factors should be entered into the process to witness the satisfaction and inner motivation of work, high quality performance, satisfaction from work, and the reduction of absenteeism and the abandonment of their employees. Because managers should be well aware that achieving high quality work life requires trust in the organization between the members, the manager, and the staff, and they are aware that when the proper workforce and the core capital of the organizations are in the direction of spirituality, the employees act beyond their duties and consider the spiritual motivation for their work. This makes them interested in their jobs and organizations, while the university is one of the important institutions that are responsible for the growth of human capital; therefore, the results of this study can help this institution to enhance their employees' sense of motivation and increase their commitment to work and trust in the organization by adopting efficient and effective leadership in their employees. In this way, by training the right leadership methods and raising the level of organizational trust in the staff, it helps to improve their relationships with each other as well as to create an attachment to the job to improve their efficiency in the organization.

Ethical considerations

Ethical issues have been completely observed by the authors.

Conflicts of interest: none

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